

Role of Islam in Reducing Social Crimes: Bangladesh Perspective

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

Islam is a complete code of life. Islam ensures security and peace in human life both worldly and life hereafter. To guide the human being in the right path and ensure security Allah the almighty gave us the holy Quran and send a model of the holy Quran to follow, our great prophet Mohammad (Sm.). Allah the almighty send Mohammad (Sm.) into the Arab society but he was sent as the blessing of the entire world. Allah the Almighty says in the Holy Quran, وَمَا أَرْسَلْنَاكَ إِلَّا رَحْمَةً لِّلْعَالَمِينَ “And We have not sent you, [O Muhammad], except as a mercy to the worlds” (1). He was sent in a time in Arab when many people of Arab used to involve in several heinous crimes. They could not distinguish between wrong and right. This age used to call (أيام الجاهلية) Dark

ABSTRACT

Social crime is becoming a common phenomenon at present days in Bangladesh. The main objective of this research is to see how we can reduce social crimes from Bangladesh by practicing Islamic rules and regulations. It is a qualitative research works where references have been used from the holy Quran, Hadith, research articles, newspaper articles. Our great prophet Mohammad (Sm.) came into a society where there were so many social crimes. People of that society were unable to distinguish between good and bad to some extent. Killing, gabbling, stealing, bribe, interest, rape were common scenarios of the Arab Society. Women did not have any dignity in society. They use to use them as their commodities and goods. This age used to call (أيام الجاهلية) Dark Age. Mohammad (Sm.) gave them the teachings of Islam and that teaching helps to reduce crimes gradually from the society. Bangladesh is a Muslim majority people's country. The research found that many Muslims of this country are not practicing Islam in their life. Killing, kidnapping, cheating, bribe, and interest have become common pictures that reflect almost every day in the different electronic and print Media. Crime is gradually spreading day by day in society. If Islamic teachings can be practice in everyday life then it can help to reduce social crime in our country.

Keywords: ISLAM, SOCIAL CRIME, REDUCING, PRACTICING ISLAM, HALAL AND HARAM, HONESTY, BANGLADESH

Age. Mohammad (Sm.) gave them the teachings of Islam and those great teachings helped to reduce crimes gradually from the society. He was able to present a secure and peaceful country by implementing Islamic laws and values. The people use to get their legal rights properly in the society as well as in the country.

Bangladesh is the third-largest Muslim majority nation in the world after Indonesia and Pakistan. The population is estimated at 161 million where about (94%) of Bangladeshis are Muslims, followed by Hindus (6.7%), Buddhists (0.6%) and Christians (0.4%) and others (2). After about a nine-month bloody War of Liberation with the supreme sacrifices of three million people and the honor of 200,000 women, Bangladesh achieved its independence on December 16, 1971. From the very beginning of its independence, the country faces different crimes, corruptions regularly which lose social security and peace. Crime can be found in Bangladesh in various forms such as Drug Trafficking, Money Laundering, Extortion, Contract Killing, Fraud, Human Trafficking, Robbery, Corruption, Black Marketeering, Violence, Terrorism, Divorce, Torture on Women, and Abduction among others. These crimes can be reduced from society by following and practicing the teachings of Islam in everyday life. The objectives of this paper are to find out the different social crimes of Bangladesh and guidelines of the holy Quran and Sunnah to reduce social crimes and ensure peace in Bangladesh.

Materials and methods

This is qualitative research work that has been done mainly by studying the Holy Quran and the Hadith of Prophet Mohammad (Sm.) which will be considered as a primary source as well as the secondary sources like journals, books and reports will be used. It also has included experiences gathered by living, observing as well as involving in different social activities in different multicultural societies at home and abroad.

Literature review

It is matter of great regret that from the very beginning of the birth of Bangladesh, it is facing the problems with crime, criminality and corruption. This problem of crime has been spreading in each and every sector of the system, e.g. politics, administration, economy, society and culture etc. Crime undermines the development efforts at various levels of a country and that it drives the depreciation of all forms of capital that is physical, human, and social and also crime is one of the key obstacles for development in Bangladesh (3). The Prophet Muhammad (Sm.) was sent to the world as a mercy to the mankind. Allah says, “And We sent thee not, but as a mercy to the all creatures” (4). The ideal society, according to the Quran is Dar As-Assalam, that is the house of Peace, Allah said, “And Allah invites to the Home of Peace and guides whom He wills to a straight path” (5). وَاللّٰهُ يَدْعُوْا اِلَى دَارِ السَّلَامِ وَيَهْدِيْ مَنْ يَّشَاءُ اِلَى صِرَاطٍ مُّسْتَقِيْمٍ (5). Abu sa'Id al-Khudri said: I heard the Messenger of Allah (Sm.) say: If any one you see something objectionable, he should change it with his hand if he can change it with his hand. But if he cannot (do so), he should do it with his tongue, and if he cannot (do so with) his tongue he should do it in his heart, that is the weakest form of faith (6).

What is social crime?

Crime has become common picture in our society. Because of crime lots of problems we face in our day life as well as it interrupts in our development work and coexistence. Crime is mainly prohibited or forbidden action by state, society, group or religion. According to Adler, Muller and Loafer, A crime is any human conduct that violates a criminal law and is subject to punishment. According to Blackstone, “crimes are public wrong and involve a violation of the duties due to the whole community” (7). The criminologist Paul Tappan defined, “Crime is an intentional act or omission in violation of criminal law committed without defense or justification” (8).

Social crimes in Bangladesh

There are many social crimes happen in different forms in our society regularly, these include drug trafficking, money laundering, extortion, killing, rape, eve teasing, dowry, fraud, human trafficking, robbery, black marketeering, political violence, corruption, terrorism, abduction, violence against man and women, etc.

Causes of social crimes in Bangladesh

People from individual to group commit crime in a society due to several reasons. Because of some fundamental needs as like as lake of food, cloth, house, education, treatment people commits crime. There are some other reasons of crimes in Bangladesh like financial crises, greed, morality crises, misguiding, political misuse, broken family, uncultured environment, social control etc.

Juvenile delinquency

The numbers of juvenile delinquents are becoming a common phenomenon at present days in different parts of Bangladesh. The number of juvenile delinquency cases is increasing day by day and the type of crimes is changing. About five hundred juvenile delinquency cases are filed every year. A recent survey shows that the number of juvenile gangs is over 60 and this number is growing at an alarming rate (9). At present days we can observe from different sources that the juvenile is involved in robbery, theft, hijacking, and extortion as well as they possess different types of deadly weapons including firearms. They are also involved in killing and rape.

Poverty

Poverty in many cases turns people into crimes. There is a common proverb in English that necessity knows no laws. Poverty is gradually reducing in Bangladesh but still a big number of the population suffering in poverty. The poverty rate has turned down from 40% in 2005 to 20.5% in 2019 in Bangladesh (10). According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, there are around 40 million children in the country between the age of 5 and 17 years. Among them, around 1.3 million children are engaged in hazardous jobs, 70% of whom are also involved in criminal activities due to poverty (11).

Drug addiction

Drug addiction is a curse for society and it is increasing gradually in Bangladesh and contributing lots to the

crimes and sufferings for the society. The Department of Narcotics Control (DNC) data shows that the number of patients with drug addiction problems has gone up alarmingly in recent times. As many as 114 patients were taking treatment at public and private rehabilitation centers on average every day in 2019. The number was 104 in 2018 and 69 in 2017. In the past five years, at least 90,133 people with drug addiction problems received treatment at five government rehabilitation centers and 53,720 at 324 private facilities. This is indicative of the fact that there has been an alarming rise in drug abuse in the country (12). At least 7500,000 people are drug addicted across the country in comparison to the 1000,000 back in 1990. If this trend continues, the number of drug abusers will be about one crore very soon. Out of the 7500,000 drug abusers, at least 65% are 15 years of age (13). Young generations are more vulnerable of the country regarding drug use. Among the drug-addicted most of them being young, between the ages of 18 and 30 years, and are from all strata of the society (14). Among the drug-addicted, 80% are youth, of whom, 50% are involved in various criminal activities. Of the total, 48% of drug addicts are educated and 40% are uneducated. Around 57% are sex offenders, while 7% are infected by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (15).

Broken family

Family calls the primary institution where children get their best moral education. But this family is breaking down significantly in Bangladesh. According to data of the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS) is that the divorce rate application has increased by a massive 34 percent throughout the country. At least 50,000 divorce applications were filed in Dhaka North and South City Corporations in the past six years, which shows on average one divorce application, was filed every hour. In Chittagong City Corporation, already 2,532 applications have been filed during January-July of this year (16). Broken families' children are mostly deprived of love, care, and cooperation in their early life. Some causes they do not get proper family education as well as institutional education. Many social scientists make opine that the broken family is contributing to the crime. Most of the causes in such kind family children become rejected from love and lack of peace (17). In some cases, women trafficking also happen because of broken family in Bangladesh. Because when they do not get proper love, care, and proper shelter then they become the victim of trafficking. Human trafficking is a repulsive phenomenon in Bangladesh and this country is a source and transit country for men, women, and children trafficked for the purposes of forced labor and commercial sexual exploitation (18). This trafficking has been occurring internally and also across the border to India, Pakistan, Malaysia, and many Middle Eastern countries (19).

Movies and pornography

Action movies and satellite channels have a negative impact on the mindset of the young generation. The violence and sex depicted in the movies incite juveniles to go together to commit unauthorized activities. Many of the photos that wind up on the site are "revenge porn" which is the pornographic souvenirs from relationships gone sour. At present time, a trend of revenge takers has been observed that they post intimate photos of the victims on Facebook and other social media. In most of the causes, women are the victims. Sometimes ex-

partners post their intimate pictures or videos just to take revenge and it turns into a business also. In many cases, women are given threats of uploading such pictures or videos just for harassing or abusing. Women face such privacy threats in a massive way in Bangladesh. As a consequence to this, every now and then victims become mentally weak and harassed, become physically ill, madness occur or as a worst-case commit suicide (20).

Role of Islam in reducing social crime

Establishing salah

Salah is one of the important pillars of Islam that make people closer to Almighty Allah as well as prevent them from committing crimes in society. Almighty Allah says, “Verily, the prayer keeps one from the great sins and evil deeds” (21). Our great Prophet Mohammed (Sm.) as mentioned in this Hadith “Pray as you have seen me praying and when it is the time for the prayer one of you should pronounce the Adhan and the oldest of you should lead the prayer” (22). In the prayer, a Muslims can connect with Allah Almighty, and remember Allah’s presence that helps a Muslim to remember Almighty Allah always. If a Muslim remembers Almighty Allah’s presence always helps him to avoid all kinds of evil things in his life.

Giving Zakah and Sadakah

One of the important causes of social crime is poverty. Zakah system in Islam can help to a great extent to remove poverty from society. In different verses of the Holy Qur’an emphasized paying Zakah. As it is mentioned in the Holy Quran, “Truly, those who believe, and do deeds of righteousness, and perform Salah (Iqamat-as-Salat), and give Zakah, they will have their reward with their Lord. On them shall be no fear, nor shall they grieve” (23). Zakah can be used as an alternative approach to poverty reduction and capacity building for the poor to be more productive, thereby contributing more to the economy. It may help to create employment opportunities by establishing small cottage industries for the less fortunate people, and create opportunities for common people to sell their goods at the local market. It may also ensure good governance and social justice in a particular society. Zakah plays an important role in reducing poverty and promotes equitable sharing of wealth. Bangladesh Government should use Zakah as a powerful tool in poverty alleviation through the institutionalization of Zakah. Zakah will not only help poverty elevation but also help to bring positive changes among the rich and wealthy people. It will clean their heart from miserliness, unnecessary wastes of money as well as save them from committing crimes in society.

Following Islamic family system

Islam introduces a very peaceful family system where every member of the family gets their rights as well as does their responsibilities properly. Muslims believe that men and women complement each other. Allah says in the Holy Quran “You are a garment to them, and they are a garment for you” (24). Family life was created by Allah to keep society together. The Quran states, “O mankind! Indeed, We have created you from male and female, and made you into nations and tribes, that you may know one another” (25). Many Muslims believe

that family life is the foundation of human society providing a secure, healthy, and nurturing environment for parents and growing children. The best place to develop human qualities such as love, care, cooperation, kindness, mercy, and compassion is in a family. In our society, we observe that the young generation does not respect elderly people even their parents. Islam has given the emphasis on respecting the older person, especially to the parents. Allah says, “Your Lord has commanded that you worship not except Him, and to parents, good treatment. If one of them or both of them reach old age with you, do not say to them a word of disrespect “uff” and do not repel them but speak them a noble word” (26). The mother is at the heart of the Muslim family and is responsible for teaching children about basic Islamic values at in early age at home. The father is responsible to bear all expenses and taking the children to the mosque. If we could follow all Islamic family cultures then we could reduce social crimes to a great extent from Bangladesh.

Distribution of wealth by following Islamic law

Many crimes happen in our society because of the improper distribution of wealth. Islam always gives guidelines for the proper distribution of wealth among the relatives as well as other people. But to some extent, people of our county are not distributing personal wealth or public wealth properly among the real owner. These types of situations bring lots of social crime in Bangladesh. Allah says, “We have distributed their livelihood among them in worldly life, and have raised some above others in the matter of social degrees, so that some of them may utilize the services of others in their work” (27). In another verse, Allah says: "In their wealth, there is a known right for those who ask for it and those who have the need for it” (28).

Prohibition of drug

Drug addiction is a serious curse on our society. Many crimes happen in Bangladesh because of drug addiction. Parents were killed by their daughter because of drug addiction in our country. Allah the Almighty knows the severe bad impact of drug addiction that’s why the drug has been prohibited strictly. Allah (SWT) says, “O you who believe! Intoxicants (all kinds of alcoholic drinks), gambling, Al-Ansab (stone altars for sacrifices to idols), and Al-Azlam (arrows for seeking luck or decision) are an abomination of Shaitan’s (Satan) handiwork. So avoid (strictly all) that (abomination) in order that you may be successful. Satan’s plan is to sow hatred and enmity amongst you with intoxicants and gambling and to hamper you from the remembrance of Allah and from prayer. Will you not give up? (29). Ibn 'Umar reported Allah's Messenger (PBUH) as saying: “Every intoxicant is Khamr and every intoxicant is forbidden” (30). Drugs are Haram and it is necessary to abstain from them. They destroy people’s lives physically, mentally, morally, and spiritually. If we could stop using all kinds of alcoholic drinks then we could reduce many social crimes in the country.

Prohibition of bribe and interest

Taking bribes and interests is a crime in Islam. Bribe and interest help to promote other crimes in society. Now a day taking bribes and interest are becoming very common practice in our country. Sometimes people show their attitude taking bribes and interests are not illegal. Allah the Almighty says: “And do not consume one

another's wealth unjustly or send it [in bribery] to the rulers in order that [they might aid] you [to] consume a portion of the wealth of the people in sin, while you know [it is unlawful]" (31). In another verse Allah says, "Allah permitted the business and forbade Riba [interest]" (32). The Messenger of Allah (Sm.) cursed the one who accepted usury, the one who paid it, the witness to it, and the one who recorded it (33). In another Hadith "The Messenger of Allah (Sm.) cursed the one who bribes and the one who takes a bribe" (34).

Proper punishment of crime

Proper punishment is very much essential to reduce social crimes. If we cannot ensure punishment properly then criminals will get encouraged to commit more crimes. Islam makes people aware of crimes always as well ensure serious punishment for the criminals in this life and life hereafter. If the criminals do prevent themselves from the crimes then Islam does not show any mercy in implementing punishment to the criminals to save humanity. Allah the Almighty says, "And there is a (guarantee of) life for you in retribution (i.e., the vengeance of murder), O wise people, so that you may guard (against bloodshed and destruction)" (35). Islam is also very much careful to save innocent people. The Quran says that God wants people to treat each other fairly and to establish justice: "God commands justice, the doing of good...and He forbids all shameful deeds and injustice" (36). In another verse, Allah says, "Stand up firmly for justice, as a witness to God, even as against yourselves or your parents or your kin, and whether it be against rich or poor" (37). We should ensure punishment for the criminals but need to be very much careful about the innocent people though they are not become victimized. Mohammad (Sm.), says "Allah would punish those who torment people in this world (without any genuine reason)" (38).

Findings

Many Muslims in Bangladesh has not enough knowledge about Islamic rules and regulations. There are mostly practices by traditions.

They practice Islam in very limited places but not all aspects of their everyday life. Many Muslims in Bangladesh give less priority to acquire Islamic knowledge from the very beginning of their life.

A big number of people are becoming drug-addicted, involve in taking bribe and interest as well as many prohibited things in Islam.

The family tie is loosening day by day as well as young generation missing family teaching in the country that turns them to the crimes.

Many Muslims people of the country do not pray five times as well they do not pay Zakah properly.

Recommendations

Islamic practice should be ensured in all aspects of life from the personal level to the state level.

To reduce juvenile crimes family bonding and family teachings should be improved.

Proper punishment should be imposed as per the degree of crime as well as careful about the innocent people.

Salat and Zakah should be ensued seriously by awareness and Islamic teachings in the society.

Islamic teaching should be introduced in society in formal and informal ways.

Conclusion

It is very clear that many crimes are occurring now and then in our society. Because of these crimes, in many cases, our development and peace are interrupting in Bangladesh. The young generation of the country is in a very risky position which is a big threat for the country. The dream of our liberation is failing for these types of crimes in society. Bangladesh is a Muslim majority country, as well as people of this country, have love and

devotion to Islam. If we could ensure Islamic practice in every aspect of life then we could reduce social crimes and ensure peace and development in the country. Our dream of golden Bangladesh will be fulfilled.

References

1. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 21, Verse 107
2. World Population prospects, Population division. population.un.org. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, 2018, Retrieved on 9 November 2019.
3. Lewis, D., Bangladesh: politics, economy and civil society. Cambridge: Cambridge, University Press, 2011
4. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 21, Verse 107
5. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 10, Verse 24
6. Sunan Abi Dawud, Hadith No: 4340, Battles (Kitab Al-Malahim) (كتاب الملاحم), Chapter: (1603), Command And Prohibition (باب الأمر والنهي)
7. Kader, M. and Hussain, M. M, Crimiology, Suchona Publishers, Dhaka, 2008, p.21.
8. Tappan, Paul, Crime, Justice and Correction, McGraw Hill, New York, 1960
9. Mannan, Majhar, Juvenile delinquency, its impact on society and remedy, The Independent, 20 November, 2020, Retrieved on March 29, 2021, from <https://www.theindependentbd.com/post/256310>
10. Voluntary National Reviews (VNRs), (2020), Accelerated action and transformative pathways: realizing the decade of action and delivery for sustainable development, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, June 2020, p.11
11. Khan. M. J. & Tipu. M.S. I. Children's involvement in crime on the rise, The Dhaka Tribune, October 1st, 2016, Retrieved on March 30, 2021, from <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/2016/10/01/childrens-involvement-crime-rise>
12. Khaled S.M.S. Alarming rise in drug abuse, The Financial Express, January 15, 2020, Retrieved on January 05, 2021, from <https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/alarming-rise-in-drug-abuse-1578932293>
13. The Daily Star, Star Online Reporter, Youth most at risk of drug abuse: Home minister, January 02, 2020, Retrieved on January 10, 2020, from <https://www.thedailystar.net/country/drug-abuse-in-bangladesh-youth-most-risk-1848514>
14. Islam. A. and Hossain. M. F., (2017), Drug abuse and its impact on Bangladesh, International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology, Vol.9 (11), p. 143, November 2017
15. Rabbi. A. R. (2019), 43% of unemployed population addicted to drugs, February 27th, 2019, Retrieved on December 20, 2020, from <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh-dhaka/2019/02/27/43-of-unemployed-population-addicted-to-drugs>
16. Nowshin. N. (2018), Understanding the rise in divorce in Bangladesh, The Daily Star, September 03, 2018, Retrieved on February, 02, 2021, from <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/opinion/perspective/understanding-the>

17. Khan, Borhan Uddin, Oporadh Biggan Porichiti.3rd (Dhaka; Provati Prokashoni,), (1995), pp.213 -15, P.167
18. Amin, (2011), Md Ruhul and Sheikh, Md Rashidul Islam, Trafficking Women and Children in Bangladesh: A Silent Tsunami of Bangladesh. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 2(4):202–211.
19. Hoque (2010), NM Sajjadul, Female child trafficking from Bangladesh: A new form of slavery. *Canadian Social Science*, 6(1):45–58.
20. Ahmed (2017), Sabbir, Sazia Sharmin Ahmed Sneha, Anwarul Kabir, Samia Jafrin, Cyber-crimes Against Womenfolk on Social Networks: Bangladesh Context, *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975 - 8887), Volume 174 - No.4, P.12
21. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 29, Verse 45
22. Sahih Bukhari-Book 11: Call to prayers (كتاب الأذان); Chapter: How the Adhan for Salat (Prayer) was started (باب بدء الأذان), Hadith 604.
23. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse 277.
24. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse 187.
25. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 49, Verse 13
26. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 17, Verse 23-24).
27. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 43, Verse 32
28. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 70, Verse 24-25.
29. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 5, Verse 90-91.
30. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse 188
31. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse 188
32. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse 275
33. Sunan Abi Dawud, Book of Commercial Transactions (كتاب البيوع), Chapter: Regarding The One Who Consumes Riba And The One Who Pays It (باب في أكل الربا وموكله), Hadith No: 3333

34. Jami` at-Tirmidhi, The Chapters On Judgments From The Messenger of Allah (كتاب الأحكام عن رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم), Chapter: What Has Been Related About The One Who Gives A Bribe And The One Who Takes A Bribe For Judgment (باب ما جاء في الرأشي والمُرْتشي في الحُكْم), Hadith No. 1337
35. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 2, Verse179
36. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, Surah 16, Verse 90
37. The holy Quran, English Translation of the meanings and Commentary, King Fahad Holy Qur-an Foundation Printing Foundation, K.S.A, The Holy Quran, Surah 4, Verse 35.
38. Sahih Muslim, Hadith No: 2613, The Book of Virtue, Enjoining Good Manners, and Joining of the Ties of Kinship (كتاب البر والصلة والآداب), Chapter: Stern Warning To One Who Torments People Unlawfully (باب الوَعِيدِ الشَّدِيدِ لِمَنْ عَذَّبَ النَّاسَ بِغَيْرِ حَقٍّ)

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